

Seasonality of overnight stays in German federal states, 1992–2024

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Core results

Seasonality of overnight stays decreased in most German federal states in the last decades: From the 16 states analysed, 13 were clearly able to decrease their seasonality level between 1992 and 2019. Mecklenburg-Vorpommern and Schleswig-Holstein have the largest decrease in the long run, but also the highest levels of seasonality.

For most of the German states (14 out of 16), international guests show a higher seasonality than national guests, with Schleswig-Holstein and Brandenburg being the only exceptions.

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Introduction

In this study we assess how seasonality of overnight stays in German federal states developed over the last decades.

This working paper uses the same methodology and indicators as the one on “Seasonality of Overnight Stays in European Countries, 1990–2024” (Schmücker, 2025). Readers are referred to that paper for more details on methodology. For this paper we again calculated the corrected Gini coefficient and the share of the top 3 months per year.

Data

Data were obtained from the *Genesis* database of the German National Statistical Office (Destatis). We used tables 45412-0025 and 0026. The database holds monthly data on overnight stays (nights spent) at tourist accommodation establishments (including camping), starting in 1992. The data are not completely coherent: Until 2010 establishments with at least nine beds and campgrounds with at least three patches were included; from 2011, establishments with at least ten beds and campgrounds with at least ten patches are included.

Data were extracted from the database in May 2025 through the publicly available database frontend (www-genesis.destatis.de).

Results

In the first section, results are reported for the total demand (national and international guests), and in the second section results are reported for national and international guests separately.

Total demand

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show that seasonality differs considerably between the 16 federal states. Highest values are found in the two states with high importance of coast tourism (Schleswig-Holstein and Mecklenburg-Vorpommern) while low values are found in the cities of Hamburg, Bremen and Berlin, but also in the states of Nordrhein-Westfalen and Hessen, which both have large urban agglomerations. The same is true für Bayern, but this state has a very large tourism demand even outside the Munich agglomeration. The plot also shows that there is no clear correlation between demand volume and seasonality. Table 1 shows the data in figures.

Table 1: Seasonality and demand volume

State	Seasonality 2024	Bed nights 2024
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	0.331	32 896 064
Schleswig-Holstein	0.311	38 089 663
Brandenburg	0.218	14 413 013
Niedersachsen	0.213	46 127 738
Rheinland-Pfalz	0.212	22 347 783
Sachsen-Anhalt	0.162	8 353 160
Bayern	0.156	102 748 512
Thüringen	0.144	10 068 249
Baden-Württemberg	0.141	58 862 894
Sachsen	0.128	19 982 287
Saarland	0.118	3 203 370
Bremen	0.087	2 918 286
Hessen	0.087	34 759 106
Hamburg	0.085	16 119 647
Berlin	0.083	30 607 084
Nordrhein-Westfalen	0.077	54 534 919

Figure 1: German federal states, bed nights and Gini coefficients, 2024

Figure 3 shows the development of seasonality over the last two decades in the 16 federal states. Clearly, there is a disruption in the years 2020 and 2021 due to the COVID crisis. 2022 and 2023 fall into the recovery period with 2024 showing seasonality values mostly on the same level as pre-COVID.

In the long term, and apart from the disruptions in the years 2020–2023, it becomes clear that most of the states were able to *decrease* their seasonality, with only three states showing a (very small) positive trend, but all of them have on a very low level.

The largest decrease can be found in the two states with the highest level of seasonality, Schleswig-Holstein and Niedersachsen, but also Bayern was able to decrease its seasonality substantially. Figure 4 shows the development of seasonality in the years 1992–2019. The three states above the zero line, Hamburg, Saarland and Sachsen-Anhalt, all have only moderate seasonality values. States below the dotted trend line were more successful in decreasing their seasonality than the states plotted above the dotted trend line: Rheinland-Pfalz had a slower decrease than Niedersachsen and Brandenburg while Bayern had a quicker decrease than Baden-Württemberg or Thüringen.

National and international demand

Splitting the overall demand into national and international segments reveals that national demand volume (overnight stays from guests living in Germany) is in most states much higher compared to international demand (guests living outside Germany, Figure 5). Differences in seasonality between segments therefore have different impact on overall seasonality.

For most of the German states (14 out of 16), international guests show a higher seasonality than national guests, with Schleswig-Holstein and Brandenburg being the only exceptions (Figure 6). In most cases, the difference is within the range of 0.01 to 0.05 points of the Gini index. Only in the cases of Rheinland-Pfalz (0.13 points) and Mecklenburg-Vorpommern (0.08 points), the difference is more pronounced.

In terms of change in the period 1992–2019, most states could decrease seasonality both in international and national demand (Figure 7). Only exemptions are Sachsen-Anhalt, Hamburg and Saarland with an increase both in national and international demand and Mecklenburg-Vorpommern being the only state with a decrease in national seasonality and an increase in international seasonality.

Figure 2: Seasonality of overnight stays in German federal states by total demand, 2024 (Gini)

Data from Destatis, analysis from NIT using the corrected Gini coefficient

Figure 3: Yearly seasonality of overnight stays in German states, 1992–2024

Data from Destatis, analysis from NIT using the corrected Gini coefficient

Figure 4: Seasonality of overnight stays vs. change in seasonality

Data from Destatis, analysis from NIT

Figure 5: National and international demand in German federal states, 2024

Data from Destatis

Figure 6: Seasonality of overnight stays in German states, 2024

Data from Destatis, analysis from NIT using the corrected Gini coefficient

Figure 7: Change in seasonality of overnight stays in German states, 1992-2019

Limitations and outlook

These data have some limitations. Specifically, the analyses on NUTS-1 level might hide more than it shows in some states. A more detailed analysis on destination level (as reported for “Reisegebiete” in German tourism statistics) would be helpful.

Even more interesting would be the search for possible causes of the decrease of seasonality. It can be hypothesised that demand grew faster than supply and that capacity limits were reached in the respective high seasons or that demand in year-round destinations (like cities) grew faster than demand in typically seasonal destination (like sun and beach). Another hypotheses could be that suppliers, including DMOs, actively (and successfully) moved the market towards less frequented seasons.

Notes

This document is a working paper of the Institute for Tourism Research in Northern Europe, Kiel. No liability is assumed for the contents.

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References

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